

"Nepalis Govern": Democratic Deliberation of Development Policies

Dear Participant,

You have been selected as one of 600 Nepalis to **represent the people as a political decision-maker** in this initiative. **No experience is needed to participate**: most people do not know how our political system works, and even the politicians you elect do not always know what is best for everyone. This is an opportunity for you to learn how your elected representatives are supposed to make decisions on your behalf. We are trying to make Nepal more democratic and inclusive in the future.

You will join other citizens in a discussion about critical development issues Nepal is facing today and prepare policy recommendations for the federal government. This type of discussion is called a **“deliberative mini-public”**. Its main purpose is to **ensure that political stakeholders take your views more seriously when making decisions on your behalf**.

You were selected through a scientific process designed to ensure a representative cross-section of Nepali society. Together with other selected participants, you will discuss your views and ideas on **two major topics**:

1. **The Distribution of Nepal’s Development Budget**
2. **Agricultural Development Priorities**

To support your preparation, we have provided you with a policy briefer. This document includes:

- Background information on the issues Nepal is facing.
- An overview of policies the government may consider to address these issues.
- Details on competing arguments for and against each policy.

We encourage you to review the policy briefer before the discussion. If your time is limited, we recommend focusing on the competing arguments in the tables, as they will provide valuable insights for the deliberation. You are invited to look at the briefer during the group discussions to find and support your position on the different topics.

After the deliberation, we will:

- Ask you to participate in a brief telephone survey to share your feedback.
- Host an event in Kathmandu where your group’s policy recommendations will be officially presented to political stakeholders.

Thank you for your commitment to our democracy,
The Organizing Team

Topic 1: Distribution of Nepal’s Development Budget

Issue

Nepal faces many development challenges. The country’s system of governance was changed only a decade ago, and many people do not yet understand how exactly this “federal” democracy works. People are seeking better work opportunities abroad, and their families depend on the remittances that they send back. Especially in rural areas, people are poorer and receive fewer government services, such as paved roads, medical treatment, and quality education. The money or “budget” that our government has to spend to solve these issues is limited. And foreign countries seem less willing to send aid to Nepal in the near future, which could further limit our budget. That means we have difficult decisions to make, and prioritize how we want our government to spend its money.

The following table lists two policies that would change how our government spends its money. There are **equally good arguments for and against each policy**.

Policy Recommendation: Should the government...	Pro Arguments	Contra Arguments
Increase the budget for agriculture?	The sector needs more investment so that farming is productive and pays well. Most of us still depend on agriculture for their livelihoods, especially women. Agriculture is an essential contributor to our economy, and makes us less dependent on other countries for food.	Increasing the budget would not help, the current budget has to be used properly. Investment in other sectors helps people to work in other sectors for higher wages. Agriculture contributes less and less to our economy, and we need economic growth to become less dependent on other countries. We can import food just as well from abroad.
Allow local governments more decision-making power to spend their money on the sectors they want?	Local officials know best in which sector money is well-spent. With education on good budgeting, local governments will be competent enough to decide where to spend money. Low-income municipalities currently have less budget autonomy, which is unfair.	Local spending should be based on national priorities. More autonomy increases the risk of corruption and mismanagement. Local officials might give more resources to high-income wards, which would be unfair.

Details

Both policies are about how the government should distribute its money or “budget”. The budget mostly comes from the taxes that we pay, but some of it also comes from international donors or is borrowed from banks.¹ Political **decision-makers first decide how to spend money between different sectors**, such as agriculture, tourism, industry, health, or education. Then for each sector, they decide how much money to spend on specific projects.

In addition, **we have three levels of government**. At the highest level is the “federal” or national government, who makes the budget for all of Nepal. In the middle are seven provincial governments, and the lowest level is made up of 753 local governments. The policies we are discussing would have to be decided by the federal government.

Policy 1: Increase the Budget for Agriculture?

Some people say the government should spend more of its budget on agriculture and less on other sectors, such as tourism, industry, or energy. Other people say the government should keep the budget for agriculture as-is. Currently the federal government is spending **3% of its budget on agriculture and livestock development**. The share of the budget in comparable sectors is **5% for the development of tourism, 12% for industry, and 20% for energy**.

Pro Arguments

Those who propose to increase the budget for agriculture say that **this would increase the income of farmers**. Most of our families (62%) still depend on agriculture for their livelihoods, especially rural households and women. Mostly men left agriculture for better prospects elsewhere, so there are more women working in agriculture than men. Even those of us who do not depend on agriculture could get **healthier food at an affordable price**. With a higher budget we can produce and **sell more products abroad, which would boost our economy**. Agriculture already makes a sizable contribution to our economy (23%), compared to other sectors like tourism or industry (which together contribute 21% to our economy and employ 17% of the population).² And if we can sell more of our produce abroad, or produce more food for ourselves, we become **less dependent on other countries**.

Contra Arguments

Others say that spending **more money for agriculture does not solve the problems** that farmers are experiencing. For example, we first need investment in infrastructure before we can make agricultural produce from rural areas available in cities. **Investing more in agriculture is not worth the cost**. People **prefer jobs outside of agriculture that give them a higher income**, for example in tourism, industry, or finance. Even those who work in

¹ Currently, 14% of the country’s budget comes from international donors, and this funding may decrease in the future if Nepal is no longer classified as a Least Developed Country by the United Nations. Countries are classified as least developed based on income, nutrition, health, education, literacy, and the stability of their economy in general. As long as Nepal ranks low on these indicators, it benefits from increased support and market access from other countries. These benefits may decrease if Nepal is no longer classified as least developed, which may or may not happen in 2083.

² The contribution to the economy is measured with the Gross Domestic Product. Gross Domestic Product represents the monetary value of goods produced and services provided in a country, and is commonly used as a general measure of economic development. But the share of an industry in a country’s Gross Domestic Product does not represent its contribution to the well-being of people, such as their life expectancy, education, or income.

agriculture may have other occupations at the same time to make a living. The **importance of agriculture for our economy has been declining for the past two decades.** Non-agricultural services and manufacturing now contribute nearly 60% to our economy. We can **import food that we cannot produce in Nepal** just as well from abroad.

Policy 2: Allow local governments more decision-making power to spend their money on the sectors they want?

This policy would change how much of their money our local governments can spend on any sector. Every year, the **federal government decides** how the money that they give to each local government should be spent. Either it must be spent on a specific sector as per the priorities of the federal and provincial governments, such as agriculture, tourism, health, or infrastructure. Or it can be spent on any of such sectors, according to the local government's priorities. This policy would increase the share of money that can be spent on any of such sectors.

Increasing the spending limit for a sector does not mean local governments get more money overall. Local officials must always follow rules when using funds, whether they decide how to spend them or follow higher government priorities. For example, the money must benefit the community, not individuals. This policy applies to regular yearly spending, planned in advance through local committees. Emergency funds, like those used for disaster relief, are separate from these budgets.

Currently, local governments can spend around one-third of their money autonomously, and two-thirds of their money as expected by federal and provincial governments.

Pro Arguments

In the few years since the new federalism system exists, the money that local governments were allowed to spend autonomously has declined. Those who want to give more autonomy say that this trend should be reversed. **Local officials have a deeper understanding of their communities' problems and appropriate solutions.** They may need more training to budget according to regulations, but can be trusted to do what is best for their community. Federal and provincial governments might want to prioritize sectors that help the country or province as a whole, but not the local municipality. More autonomy also **reduces inequality between low-income and high-income municipalities.** Municipalities who collect more taxes generally receive a higher budget ceiling from the federal government, which means they have more budget to spend. By comparison, the municipalities who collect less taxes are limited in their spending capacity. This means they cannot invest enough in projects that promise to generate more income in the future. Giving more autonomy to local governments would help them **feel more empowered and involved** in development projects, which would improve their impact.

Contra Arguments

Other people do not want to give local governments more autonomy. They say that **the risk of funds being misused or diverted is too great.** According to the Commission for the Investigation of Abuse of Authority, half of complaints are directed at local officials, a third at federal-, and the rest at provincial-level officials. Until they learn how to spend their budget more appropriately, federal and provincial governments should make more decisions about what is best for local communities. **Local officials would not spend enough on projects that align with national priorities.** In low-income municipalities, officials could

invest more in wards that already have a high income, to increase the municipalities' income even more. This might **increase inequality between wards**, even if it decreases inequality between municipalities.

Topic 2: Agricultural Development Priorities

Issue

Nepali agriculture faces a lot of challenges. **More and more land is left fallow** or is farmed by already **overburdened woman household members**, as men are more likely to migrate for employment in other sectors. Some farmers are using too many chemicals on their farms to increase productivity. Especially in the Hill and Mountain regions **modern farming technology is not accessible**, and more **extreme weather will make farming even more difficult** in the future. Ultimately **these issues impact all of us, as they increase food prices and unemployment**, and decrease the availability and quality of food in local markets.

Because the agriculture budget is limited, we have to either accept or reject both of the following policies. There are equally good arguments to accept and reject both policies.

Policy Recommendation: Should the government...	Pro Arguments	Contra Arguments
Reduce subsidies and grants for farmers?	Subsidies and grants are costly and unsustainable, especially for chemical fertilizer. Over-use of chemical fertilizer can be harmful for farmers, soil health, and consumer health. The government is bad at distributing subsidies timely and fairly.	We would have to pay more for food, and become more dependent on food imports from other countries. The income of farmers would decrease, especially in Terai. If we invested more in subsidies, the government would be better at distributing them to the farmers who need it the most, like women-led households and marginalized farmers.
Increase budget for technology research and training for farmers?	Helps farmers produce more or better food in the long-run, making us less dependent on food imports and more resilient to climate change. It would help solve problems such as pest control, weed management, and soil health. This could make technologies more helpful for women-led households.	Prioritizing technology would decrease funding for farmer's immediate needs and productivity. That means food would become more expensive. The benefits of technology are not as visible and would take a long time to realize. Access to technology could be an issue because of poor infrastructure. We do not know for sure if new technologies will help farmers.

Details

Because the agriculture budget is limited, it is not possible to support all policies at the same time. The more policy-makers support subsidies for farmers (reject the first policy), the less they can support funding for technology and training (accept the second policy). In the same way if they want to increase funding for technology, policy-makers would have to reduce funding for subsidies. Another way to think about this is that each policy stands for a “model” of agriculture: the “subsidize inputs” model where the government ensures that there is enough staple food for everyone **today**, and the “research technology” model where the government ensures that food production for everyone will be sustainable **in the future**.

Policy 3: Reduce Input Subsidies for Farmers?

Currently, **most of the government subsidies are for fertilizer**. These subsidies make up **almost half of the budget for agriculture** (49%). Most of this money is used to buy chemical fertilizer abroad, and distribute it to farmers. Recently the government invested in a facility to produce chemical fertilizer in Nepal. A relatively small amount is invested in organic fertilizer.³

The government also subsidizes the production of selected crops through purchases from farmers with a **minimum support price program**. This is a form of subsidy that guarantees a certain price for selected crops before they are planted. The goal is to protect farmers from traders (“middlemen”) who may not offer fair market prices for their produce. Sometimes if farmers cannot sell their product at the minimum price, the government buys it from them. For example this year, the government purchased around 1% of the rice produced in Nepal through this program. The government also **subsidizes certain types of seeds** to encourage the use of more productive variants.

Pro Arguments

Those who want to decrease input subsidies say that they are **unsustainable in the long-run**. Chemical fertilizer degrades soil health over time, making fields more vulnerable to more extreme weather events caused by climate change, and can make food less healthy for consumers. **Especially for vulnerable consumers**, such as elderly people or pregnant women, **over-use of chemical fertilizer causes health issues**. With subsidies it has been difficult to move farmers from chemical to more sustainable fertilizers and pest management, because that typically leads to a decrease in productivity for several seasons. Subsidies are also **not distributed effectively**. For example, the government did not manage to purchase as much fertilizer as intended from India. And the minimum support price is announced too late to affect the decisions of farmers which crops they should plant, in addition to being relatively low. **Consumers can buy food from India at a lower price anyways**. Our farmers cannot compete with Indian farmers even with the subsidies, because India offers higher subsidies than our government can afford. For example, Indian farmers can sell their rice 20-30% cheaper.

³Fertilizer is applied to supply plants with nutrients that help them grow. Chemical fertilizer allows industrial farming that increases the productivity of food systems. It is mostly produced abroad and then imported to Nepal via state-owned companies. Its price largely depends on international markets. Organic or natural fertilizer is produced by farmers themselves and some businesses in Nepal, using animal dung as a main ingredient. Officially the government subsidizes entrepreneurs who produce organic fertilizer up to 50%.

Contra Arguments

Those who want to keep or increase the subsidies say that they are **necessary for agricultural productivity and farmer welfare**. Without the subsidies we would be **more dependent on other countries like India for our food**. Without timely supply of high-quality fertilizer, farmers especially in the Terai **risk losing their produce and income**. They might resort to low-quality fertilizer that produces even less healthy food in the market. Smallholder farmers especially struggle to obtain enough fertilizer. The **demand for chemical fertilizer is almost three times higher than the supply**. Meanwhile, the minimum support price **protects farmers from unfair market practices**. If the government does not guarantee a price, even more farmers might leave agriculture. All of this means more expensive food for consumers, and especially poorer families might not be able to afford it. Just because subsidies are not managed well does not mean that we should give up on them: **with higher subsidies, the government would be better at distributing them**. For example, farmers in the hills and mountains might receive more organic fertilizer, more chemical fertilizer could be made available to farmers in the Terai, and the minimum support price program could be expanded. We could become **self-sufficient in staple foods** much faster with higher subsidies than with lower subsidies.

Policy 4: Increase budget for technology research and training for farmers?

Nepal's agricultural research and training is mainly led by government-run institutions. With the budget they receive, these institutions **develop technologies that improve agricultural productivity**, and through farmers' participatory research and collaboration, the **knowledge is shared, distributed and taught**. For example, we can design seeds that can produce more food despite extreme weather conditions, "climate-smart" tools like solar-powered irrigation, more efficient cold storage, and land management techniques. **This year, the government spent almost 10% of the agriculture budget on research and training** (including cold storage solutions).

Pro Arguments

Some people say that research and development increases the contribution of agriculture to our economy. **This will decrease poverty, provide food security and reduce food prices in the long-run**. Slow development of the agriculture sector can be attributed to farmer's limited access to modern technologies. For example, China has experienced agricultural growth over the years that can be partly explained by shifting investments from input subsidies to research and technology. Most of our farmers currently have to reuse seed varieties from previous seasons for lack of alternatives. **Quality seeds could increase crop yields** by 15 to 25%, and **reduce the need for chemical fertilizers and pesticides**. The development of climate-resilient seeds could allow **crops to survive extreme weather events and ensure that we have enough food in the long-run**. In addition, with better technology such as cold storage farmers could better commercialize their products, **making high-quality, healthier food available to people across Nepal**, for example the famous Jumla apples. This also reduces food waste, because farmers cannot currently sell all their products in local markets before they perish.

Contra Arguments

Other people say that research and development **does not give many benefits** in the short-run. Even after new approaches and technologies are developed and tested, most farmers won't be able to access them, especially women and marginalized farmers. There is a risk that **mostly large, commercial farmers can access the technology**. It will take years of additional investment to make modern technologies accessible, especially to smallholder farmers in rural areas. Some farmers are also **slow to change**, even if they are offered training. In the meantime, **food prices would increase**, and we would become **more dependent on other countries for food**. Many of us **cannot afford high-quality produce** that would be commercialized with this approach. Instead, government-run institutions could **spend existing money more equally and effectively**. The **private sector should be engaged** instead, as they are also profiting from improved agricultural production. The government could create rules to help with that.